

D2: Mapping strategy available (based on domain specific knowledge and HMC requirement); first trial version set up.

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Introduction

In the MetaMap³ project, metadata of domain health, environment and earth observation are compiled, enriched and pooled together. The project partners contribute with metadata of the children cohorts GINI and LISA¹ (HMGU), drought monitor^{2,3} (UFZ) and land cover⁴ (DLR).

The aim of deliverable D2 is to define a joint mapping strategy for the linkage of metadata of the three domains. We developed an approach to align the metadata to a common structure and format. Firstly, we identified as the main mapping criteria spatial and time coverage. For the environmental metadata and the epidemiological metadata that have a spatial component (study centers, recruitment districts) we converged to the standard ISO 19115⁵ and to the eXtensible Markup Language (XML). Secondly, we compiled a decision matrix to guide the selection of a suitable application to upload and store the harmonized metadata. Building on this conceptual work we identified a catalog to store a subset of our cross-domain metadata.

Mapping strategy

Each scientific field has a different focus. Analogously, the metadata used within the three domains come with different requirements and vary in origin, format and scope, so they cannot be merged routinely. To overcome these limitations a joint mapping strategy has to be defined. Three mapping approaches have been taken into consideration:

- a) 1:X mapping, in which all partners adopt an external metadata schema;
- b) 1:1 mapping, in which the metadata of each domain is mapped bilaterally;
- c) 1:1 mapping, in which two partners converge to the standard of the third domain.

Figure 1 graphically represents the different mapping concepts. The 1:X mapping concept assumes that the metadata of all involved partners have to migrate towards one central metadata schema. The mapping is unidirectional as the domain-specific schemas are mapped onto a common schema. In the 1:X mapping concept, none of the partners has the metadata ready in the external schema and an *ad hoc* solution has to be found. The approach is demanding in terms of the initial setup effort, however it scales well, as more schemas are added to the system.⁶ The 1:1 mapping concept assumes a decentralized approach, in which the metadata of each domain is mapped bilaterally. There is no common schema that serves as *lingua franca* and the mapping between different domains has to be performed in both directions. The 1:1 mapping concept has the challenge of requiring separate mapping solutions. For each connecting line, a different mapping has to be agreed upon. The more domains are involved, the more individually tailored mapping solutions are required. In the 1:1 mapping, the domains Health and Earth & Environment would converge towards the ISO 19115⁵, which has already been adopted by the domain Aeronautics, Space &

Transport. This approach has the advantage of converging towards a well-established and widely used standard. Using a standard, which is maintained by the International Organization for Standardization is attractive for possible additional partners from other domains.

Figure 1. Graphical representation of different mapping concepts. Domains are color-coded as follows: domain Health is shown in red, green stands for Earth & Environment and blue for Aeronautics, Space & Transport.

For MetaMap³, we finally decided to perform the 1:1 mapping which requires the adoption of ISO 19115⁵, a geographic information metadata standard. The metadata mapping is then performed by location (spatial coverage) and date (time coverage). The rationale behind the choice of spatial information as mapping criteria comes from the importance of georeferenced data in the epidemiological research. Use of georeferenced environmental and health data has found its way in the field of environmental medical research in the past 30 years.⁷ It started with the investigation of small-scale disease clusters (e.g. linked to nuclear power plants) and spatial data of air pollutants for exposure estimation. The most important environmental factors that influence health include air pollution, noise, greenspace, imperviousness, chemicals and climatic conditions.⁸⁻¹⁵ Linking GIS data to medium and large cohort studies allows to evaluate risks factors to the health of future generations.⁷

Beside the spatial component, the metadata of the three project partners is mapped with respect to time. To have an accurate assessment of the influence of environmental factors over health, the general user, in this case an epidemiologist, is interested in a specific date or time interval. In most cases, the time period during which the health information of the participants to a cohort study is available has to match the time period of the exposure assessment. The general user queries the data based on time. For this reason, it is important to align our metadata with respect to time and use a joint date format.

In the 1:1 mapping, the metadata of the drought monitor that are stored as NetCDF are mapped to the ISO 19115 standard⁵. The metadata stored in the NetCDF headers is compiled according to conventions, for example following the NetCDF-CF Climate and Forecast conventions, and is less standardized in comparison to ISO 19115⁵. Currently, there is no established convention for NetCDF headers at UFZ and the geolocation is not fully written into the header. For the epidemiological metadata that have a spatial component (study centers, recruitment districts) it is possible to converge towards the standard ISO 19115⁵. Health metadata that do not fit in the categories of a geospatial metadata schema, have to be stored separately. Features of the Health metadata that cannot fully integrated into this mapping concept

have to be uploaded into a domain-agnostic platform or in catalogs that follow domain specific requirements. For example, cohorts' metadata can be uploaded into the Maelstrom catalog^{16,17} or into the NFDI4health StudyHub¹⁸ portal.

The mapping will be performed using the R package *geometa*¹⁹. *Geometa*¹⁹ allows to convert geographic metadata from one standard to another. In our case, the drought monitor metadata stored as NetCDF objects and modeled in R with *ncdf4*²⁰ can be mapped to ISO metadata. The spatial component of the GINI-LISA metadata can be written to XML according the ISO 19115⁵ standard. The metadata stored as XML is machine-readable. A workflow was devised to transform base cohort information in an ISO 19115⁵ compliant manner without exposing sensitive information about participants' data. In the first step of the workflow the spatial information pertaining to the area of the cohort study is defined. For the GINI cohort the polygons of the municipalities Munich and Wesel are stored as a GeoPackage file (GPKG). The spatial information is then supplemented by the health metadata in aggregated form. In our example, GINIplus COVID-19 questionnaire questions are labeled according to the Maelstrom¹⁶ classification into 18 categories and appended to the attribute table of a GPKG file. Based on the GeoPackage file, an XML file is created which can be jointly queried with metadata of the other domains.

Metadata catalog

To assist the choice of the optimal application to host the metadata we compiled a decision matrix. The decision matrix shown in Table 1 rates different applications against seven criteria. A score between 1 and 5 is assigned to the platforms based on the requirements. The higher the score the better the platform fits the selection criteria. The scores are weighted based on the importance of the requirement for our project. The requirement criteria are ordered top to bottom according to the assigned weights. The decision matrix includes technical requirements and criteria inspired by the FAIR Data principles²¹. As first requirement, the ability to store spatial metadata is set. This criteria is essential since the mapping will be performed by location (spatial coverage) and date (time coverage). Native built-in support for storage of spatial metadata will allow to store the metadata from the three domains into the ISO 19115 standard. We want our platform to be accessible from the perspective of the general user, which is a user with domain knowledge, but no advanced programmatic or computational skills.²² A general user should be able to find the metadata that is relevant for the respective project. For this reason, we assigned high weights to the criteria "search tools" and "visualization" in the decision matrix. The ability to store non-spatial metadata schema is also considered. In fact, the application has to be flexible in terms of adding further heterogeneous metadata from the partners but also other sources. Next, validation tools are taken into consideration. Conformity checkers and validators are important to ensure that the metadata is stored according to high data quality standards. Furthermore, the setup effort of the data infrastructure provider, which is the effort of installing, configuring and running the application has to be taken into account. Finally, it should be possible to customize the application via plugins, source editors or similar tools. This requirement is termed as "extendibility" in the decision matrix.

Table 1. Decision matrix of potential hosting applications. Score between 1 (low) and 5 (high) indicates the degree of suitability of the platform with regard to the selection criteria.

Requirement	Weight	Application			
		GeoNetwork	QGIS Server / QGIS Server Catalog	MetaStore2	R-Shiny custom application
Native built-in support for storage of spatial metadata	0.3	5	3	1	2
Search tools	0.25	5	3	2	4
Visualization	0.15	5	4	1	3
Ability to store non-spatial metadata schema	0.1	3	1	5	4
Validation tools	0.1	5	1	4	3
Ease of setup	0.05	5	5	3	1
Extendibility	0.05	3	3	4	5
Total Score		4.70	2.85	2.20	3.05
Rank		1	3	4	2

Four applications were taken into consideration: two well-established GIS applications and two domain agnostic solutions. The GIS applications are: GeoNetwork²³, a catalog of geospatial metadata records, and QGIS Server²⁴, which includes a web map service (WMS) and a simple catalog. Both application are open source. GeoNetwork is tailored to host metadata records. It supports multiple standards from ISO to the Dublin core. Metadata can be uploaded directly to the catalog as XML, MEF or ZIP. The data curator can add records using a user-friendly Web Editor. GeoNetwork has geospatial-temporal search capability and includes validation tools. On the other hand, QGIS Server main functionality is the web map service. The catalog that comes with QGIS shows the list of projects served by the server and the associated metadata. To the best of our knowledge, QGIS Server does not include validation tools. MetaStore2²⁵ and custom R-Shiny application²⁶ are domain-agnostic solutions. They are flexible and suited to host metadata with domain-specific requirements. R-Shiny can benefit from a multitude of packages suited for dealing with geospatial information, such as geometa¹⁹, sf^{27,28}, raster²⁹. However, writing a custom R-Shiny application will require extensive programming and high setup effort compared to the alternatives. The application has to be tailored to solving a specific metadata issue. MetaStore2 is a metadata repository and schema registry service. It comes ready-to-use and with an extensive documentation. MetaStore2 includes the possibility to validate a record against a given schema. As limitation it must be mentioned that complex metadata structures, such as geospatial metadata schemas, are difficult to model and maintain within MetaStore2 perspective.

Based on our project requirements, GeoNetwork²³ scored the highest. The application is built around the ISO 19115 standard and prominently indicates spatial and temporal overlaps in the metadata catalog. Figure 2 shows the mapping strategy that was selected and highlights the tools to support its implementation. We already set up a test instance of the GeoNetwork²³ catalog which is hosted on a

server at HMGU. Currently, we are populating the catalog with our metadata use cases. By the end of the project, we plan to release the platform to other researchers working in thematically related fields.

Figure 2. Graphical representation of the selected mapping concept and screenshot of our GeoNetwork instance.

For the subset of health metadata, that does not include spatial information, we explored the upload into domain-specific catalogs. We generated four GINI-LISA metadata resources for the NFDI4health StudyHub (an inventory of German health studies on COVID-19)¹⁸. Our entries are currently under review. Additionally we are exploring the possibility of uploading FHIR³⁰ schemas into MetaStore²⁵.

Summary

In order to link the metadata across the domains of health, environment and earth observation, three metadata mapping strategies were taken into account. After weighing the benefits and limitations of the different approaches, we agreed to implement a 1:1 mapping, in which two partners converge to the standard of the third domain. A first pilot version was drafted. The R package geometa¹⁹ was used as mapping tool to bring the metadata of the health and environment domains to the ISO 19115 standard⁵. The metadata was saved in an eXtensible Markup Language tree and uploaded into a common platform. Four applications were taken into consideration for the hosting of the harmonized geospatial metadata. The fitness-for-purpose of the application was assessed, based on our metadata and on the project requirements. Among the decision criteria, we considered technical requirements such as the setup effort and the ability to customize the platform with plugins. The decision matrix includes criteria inspired by the FAIR Data principles.²¹ The FAIR principles apply not only to data in the conventional sense, but also to the data infrastructure and to algorithms.²¹ For example, to account for "findability" we considered the filtering and search tools options of the application. We considered "interoperability" by reviewing platforms with respect towards native built-in support of internationally well-established metadata schemas and open API backends. As main platform we decided to store our resources into a GeoNetwork²³ catalog.

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